

THE CONTENT OF PEDAGOGICAL FORMATION OF CREATIVE COMPETENCE IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the issue of developing creative competence in students from a pedagogical perspective. The knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary for the formation of students' creative competence are analyzed. The role, tasks of teachers, and pedagogical technologies in the process of developing these qualities are also outlined. The article also provides practical recommendations for the formation of students' creative competence.*

Keywords: *pedagogical skills, creative competence, professional communication, pedagogical conditions, education.*

Main part: The process of bringing the higher education system in our country to the international level of education system is the development of modern pedagogical learning conditions in the educational process of the higher education institution, which ensures the synchronization of methodological approaches and principles for the effective formation of the main components of creative competence and makes the problem of its implementation even more urgent.

Creative competence in a person forces higher education to make adjustments to the training of graduates in order to accumulate experience and decision-making ability.

Primary education in the 21st century is related to the dynamic changes taking place in the science and educational process, and relies on the integrative role of the future specialist, including: an integral process of the education; analytical thinking; set of skills and abilities; critical assessment of existing or potential problems; contextual understanding of the field and situation; the ability to constantly update one's knowledge and adapt to changes in education and educational requirements in society throughout the entire working life; the ability to synthesize innovations in their design and training phases, etc.

Pedagogical process is considered as a sufficiently complex, multifaceted, constantly changing integral phenomenon. It combines the processes of human formation, comprehensive development, upbringing, education, as well as all the conditions of this process.

In the science of modern pedagogy, pedagogical conditions are considered as external and internal conditions that contribute to or hinder the influence of personality development factors. For example: readiness for creative activity, environmental stimulation, support of material, educational resources, etc. In a broad sense, conditions, reasons, various factors of development, technologies, methods, technical and software tools of teaching, education, management process support, pedagogical support and interaction is interpreted as a secret.

Successful formation of the creative competence of students of pedagogical higher educational institution is guaranteed only if the following basic pedagogical conditions exist:

A positive attitude towards the selected pedagogical activity and the presence of a constant need for creative self-improvement (a clear idea formed by the student about the content of the future pedagogical activity; strengthening creative motivation; actively involving students in professionally oriented activities; continuous professional reflection).

Introducing students to the future specialty in real practical activities (professionalism of teachers working in higher education; effective management of educational, scientific and creative activities of students; creation of a creative environment in a higher education institution; pedagogical function of a teacher; positive, moral and psychological climate of educational institution).

Creative self-education and activation of self-education (targeted independent work of students on self-improvement; creative self-education; implementation of educational programs of higher education; students professionalism in teaching).

During our research, we identified the following organizational and pedagogical conditions that help to form the creative competence of future primary school teachers (Figure 1):

Figure 1. Pedagogical conditions that help to form creative competence of future elementary school teachers

We found it necessary to pay special attention to the characteristics of the pedagogical conditions described in the diagram above.

In the scientific works of a number of scientists who have conducted research in this field, it is emphasized that the creation of an innovative and creative environment is important as a high desire for innovation and creativity in the educational process. Creation and dissemination of innovations is a purposeful process that includes the acquisition of new technology, its creative understanding and improvement of practical results.

The creative environment can effectively influence the joint activities of the teacher and the student, help them to understand each other and eliminate conflicting situations based on mental and social readiness.

Pedagogical creativity implies that the teacher has a high level of competence in his field, as a result of which pedagogical creative activity will be more effective and successful. One of the most important indicators of pedagogical creativity is creative well-being and pedagogical creativity.

It should be emphasized that future elementary school teachers should be fully trained and developed, taking into account their talent and potential level, so that they can fully demonstrate their hidden abilities.

Teaching creative activities in the higher education system is considered as an activity that serves to improve a number of qualities of a creative person. Mental activity; ingenuity; the desire

to acquire new knowledge necessary for specific practical activities; independence in identifying and solving existing and potential problems in the field of education; diligence and responsibility; competitiveness etc.

It follows from this that it is necessary to consider the development of the creative personality as a continuous process and to rely on the development of previously formed creative abilities in the conditions of an educational institution.

The educational process, based on the principle of continuity and systematicity, performs the task of developing new knowledge - types of creative competence that may be far from individual practical knowledge, therefore, if the student is given choice and creative freedom, creative development can be successful.

Openness to processes and events, the desire to learn and self-respect, self-confidence, together with the creation of a creative environment aimed at achieving a high level of creative activity and knowledge by students, acquiring creative skills and abilities is the basis for the development of creative competence.

In order to implement the strategy of long-term development of the education and social sphere in our country, it is necessary to introduce innovations based on modern information and communication technologies into the educational process and skills.

"Ability is not reduced to skill, but an unskilled specialist cannot perform his main work as a person, that is, he does not provide the speed, depth and power of mastering the methods of action" said by G.A. Zuckerman.

Taking into account that the potential of general creative and special subjects and the whole range of pedagogical tasks help to create an innovative-creative environment in pedagogical higher education institutions, we created an innovative-creative environment as a condition for the formation of students' abilities, successful completion of assigned tasks, new knowledge and experience was responsible for the acquisition of knowledge and skills, as a result of which the experience of innovative activity of students was formed and they became its subjects.

In pedagogy and psychology, the category of subjectivity takes a strong place as a fundamental characteristic of a person. The active activity of the subject is a condition for the action of one or another piece of objective reality as an object and is given to the subject in forms of activity, while the forms of reproduction in knowledge that reflect the characteristics of objective reality are among the forms of activity that change the subject at the same time.

Modern pedagogy considers the subject as a person who can master this activity and creatively change reality, a creator of his life, a person who can build strategies and tactics of his life, and a person who is in the process of self-evaluation of himself and his activities.

K.A. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya interprets subjectivity as a person's ability and opportunity to influence the process of his life activity. "Determining one's professional tasks under existing conditions, acting independently and coordinating one's actions with others, connecting common and personal tasks and goals, determining their opportunities due to circumstances, etc."

A.V. Brushlinsky mentions the following characteristics of the subject: "this is a person, each of them is the highest level of activity, integrity, autonomy".

O.S. Nikitin, V.A. Sonin, S.R. Ivanov, V.A. Korolkova's work based on the analysis, we can call the category of subjectivity "internal position", integrative "personality of the future specialist", self-improvement in the field of professional activity, creativity and reflexivity. Becoming a subject of creative activity means mastering its existing types, gaining sufficient

knowledge and experience, being ready to implement this activity and creatively change it, that is, to strive for self-realization.

"It is in the elimination (overcoming) of known and real, desirable and really possible relations, which require the tension of all forces comparable to the performance of this creative activity, that the subject of action realizes his potential at the creative level, i.e. asserts himself, acts as a person who creates spiritual and practical life conditions".

The formation of subjective position of the person in the process of dialogic communication is reached through performing all types and forms of student's educational activities (listening and recording lectures, talking with the audience, solving problems, conducting discussions, defending the position), planning one's work and through the ability to organize.

Mastering the experience of professional communication and behavioral methods (creative ethics, communication style), cooperation and working in a group for a common result - searching for the meaning of value orientations related to relationships, forming communicative competence and self-realization is the motivation to organize.

In the process of forming a person as a subject of activity, motivation is an integral part of pedagogical conditions, the leading regulator of student's active position. The subjective position of the student has "characteristics of the level" and ensures person's activity in learning, helps to achieve the educational goal, and realizes the professional self.

At the same time, not only the level of skills developed at work, but also confidence in their effectiveness is important. Ability is the main condition of successful activity. Student's knowledge of his scientific potential gives a sufficient idea of himself and his capabilities. Satisfying personal needs is the transition to self-realization - "the desire to fully identify and develop one's personal potential; true self-realization presupposes the existence of favorable social conditions".

E.N. Bogdanova, Z.I. Trumaseva, N.R. Shcherbak consider self-awareness to be the main motivational factor of human readiness for activity based on the desire for perfection, and emphasize that it reflects the path of life - one's activities and successes.

The pedagogical activity of the teacher and the cognitive and creative activity of the future specialist change with the creation of an innovative and creative environment, which serves to reflect student's self and improve creative abilities.

During our research work, we considered reflection to be an important mechanism for effective thinking; as a special organization of the processes of understanding what is happening in the context of a wider system, including the evaluation of situations and actions, search for methods and operations for solving problems as a process of active understanding of the situation and actions of the person and other people involved in self-analysis and problem solving.

Based on the study of student's future change, a permanent understanding of the desire to express change is formed. Creative activity allows the most effective and sufficient use of important processes that ensure development and self-improvement. It improves the creative process of research, the success and quality of its best work.

The development of future student's skills and abilities ensures his awareness of the expanded curriculum, its conceptual apparatus, sequence and content. The development is manifested in the fact that traditional education focuses on self-education based on self-analysis, self-evaluation and self-correction.

Therefore, the tendency to think is considered as an important factor in the formation of skills. The ability to think is one of the main characteristics of a good person. The ability to control not only work results, but also the level of creativity determines the effectiveness of solving educational problems. Conducting effective research and practice is a key success factor for future professional activities.

The formation of creative competence is mainly ensured by future teacher's awareness of the appropriateness of subject information, its logical structure and content, and reflexivity is the self-analysis of traditional education, manifested in self-education based on self-evaluation and self-correction.

Thus, the pursuit of reflection is the main condition for the formation of creative competence, the ability to reflect is an indicator of a creative person. The ability to consciously control not only the results of one's work, but also the level of creativity determines the effectiveness of solving educational problems and helps to form professional competence, when previous experience in qualitatively changed conditions does not give positive results in professional activity.

The main condition for the successful formation of the creative competence of future primary school specialists is the effective management of their educational, scientific and professional activities. If the influence of the teacher is aimed at involving the future teacher in the development of "necessary integrated professional experience" and has a purposeful nature, the creative activity becomes the creativity of students.

It has been proven that a student can acquire creative competence by solving problems independently. This requires him to be ready to apply the necessary knowledge and skills in practical activities.

Pedagogical scientists such as N.S. Glukhanyuk, Ye.N. Shiyanov, Ye.F. Zeer, V.D. Shadrikov believe that the development of future teacher's activity at the stage of creative preparation depends on the integrity of the pedagogical process and educational-cognitive, as well as scientific knowledge that requires special knowledge, skills, qualifications and abilities for effective implementation and they emphasize that it happens in practical (creative) activities, as well as professional conditions.

The lack of unity of these types of activities leads to a conflict between the goal of education and the results of creative training. Eliminating this conflict is possible when changing the purpose and content of student activities based on state educational standards. Such activity is considered as a unity of goals, motives, actions, and results, which creates a basis for strengthening the practice-oriented teaching direction and developing student's professional competence, his subjective position.

Psychologists say that "only by having practical contact with the outside world, changing it purposefully and creatively, a person can change not only the surrounding world, but also himself in this complex interaction process".

The task of the teacher is to create conditions for professionally important learning of the student personality based on self-teaching, self-management and self-knowledge. With this understanding, teaching is equated with the professional formation of a person. P.I. Pidkasisty defined professional self-education as a purposeful, systematic, cognitive-research activity aimed at developing professionally important qualities of one's personality through professional self-education.

As mentioned above, the acquisition of knowledge, skills and creative experience is carried out at the theoretical, practical and functional levels.

In our opinion, a graduate of a pedagogical university has a theoretical level, that is, an advanced level of knowledge of the scientific foundations of future creative activity, because the traditional system of training university students first of all forms fundamental knowledge. The practical level refers to the system of organizing practical training according to the "action algorithm - modified algorithm - creativity" scheme. Practical training based on theoretical knowledge is aimed at developing practical skills and forming educational, organizational, communicative, creative, reflexive skills and abilities necessary for a future primary school teacher which helps to determine the level of mastery of professional competencies.

Organization of practical work, depending on its complexity, includes technological, situational and functional levels of solving educational problems. The technological level describes the operational side of professional activity; the situational level repeats the content aspect of future professional activity and determines the sequence of thematic-logical actions based on the accumulated experience and acquired knowledge; the functional level is aimed at modeling professional activity in general and describes its structural-functional, dynamic side.

Functional competencies include knowing the methods of analysis, the interrelationship of pieces of information to establish connections between them, separating information for establishing and making decisions, and critically evaluating information for judgments, facts and their analysis. As a result, all this helps to form the ability to maintain and design professional activities from the goal to the result.

Improving the methodology for developing the creative competence of a future specialist is a specific level of involving students in complex types of educational and cognitive creative activities, in which the main goals and tasks, independent skills must be acquired by students in special subjects development and support of knowledge of technology and mastering the process of self-monitoring and self-evaluation.

As mentioned above, as one of the conditions for the success of teaching special subjects in the formation of the creative competence of future teachers, the role of modeling education and solving educational problems that ensures the strengthening of the practical orientation and serves as a criterion of the level of knowledge and a measure of competence is of great importance. At the same time, the educational tools used help to develop not only knowledge, but also personal qualities and abilities.

In the process of practical work, when solving educational problems, the student acquires the experience of the work he has chosen and tries to determine whether the nature of this work corresponds to his abilities and skills.

It is known that the educational problem models a problematic situation based on educational conflict as a professional problem.

Educational problem solving is related to trying to solve the problem, and the willingness to solve it is the basis of professional competence.

Creating an innovative and creative environment is an important condition for the organization of the educational process, in which the statement of the task is included as a stage of activity and is the result of the stage of solving the task. The use of non-standard creative educational tasks of open type (no single correct solution), problem analysis, modeling of creative situations and encouraging students' self-confidence in their specific knowledge implies having a

reserve of experience, as well as patterns of searching for creative solutions and creative behavior, in other words, it depends on creative competence.

"Through the educational task, a field of cognitive activity is created for the student", a sequence of tasks is organized with the condition of mastering the approximate bases of actions, execution algorithms.

It follows that the creative training of a specialist is a complex, multi-level, multi-directional, systematic mental product, first of all, a personal product of a person. In psychological-pedagogical literature, preparation for activity is considered as the initial state of behavior implementation. This is the existence of a specific behavior image and a constant orientation to its implementation, a certain mechanism of orientation to the implementation of professional tasks.

The result of creative training is the development of psychological-pedagogical readiness of students of pedagogical higher education institutions to implement the pedagogical process. In this case, it is assumed that through student's ability to build future creative activities, study independently, describe and explain pedagogical phenomena, accept grounded professional solutions, search independently for scientific-pedagogical knowledge, and participate positively in interaction with the pedagogical goal of thinking and acting he has mastered the skill of doing.

In the creative preparation of the student, the communicative preparation of the person takes a leading place.

Communicative preparation is a high level of student's speech culture, his ability to use language and words correctly. The level of student's speech development is an important indicator of student's communicative readiness, and this readiness is an indicator of the development of his professional thinking.

Implementation of the process of creative self-development of students, the existence of a program of personal creative-pedagogical self-improvement, mastering the theoretical foundations of self-education of the content of academic subjects, systematic training of self-education are the use of opportunities provided for in the variable part of the curriculum.

Thinking is focused on the search for connections and includes interconnection according to signs: difference-similarity; cause and effect; real-possible; clarification of relations. Action is a clear and partial result of thinking.

Pedagogy is one of the main rules of the systematic-active approach to teaching in a higher educational institution - it is a clearly defined direction of the educational process aimed at forming logical thinking in students.

For example, the organization of teaching through the active introduction of computer technologies and network communications into the educational process has become an integral element of pedagogical activity, which determines the construction of a new form of education that meets the needs of the information society.

The use of computing, information, telecommunication technologies and systems effectively affects the solution of professional tasks and the educational and training process, expands communication opportunities, "fulfills the needs of functional interaction of educational subjects".

Mental activity leads to self-transformation and creative problem-solving. "The success of a solution depends on reproducing what is known, creatively rearranging existing knowledge and incorporating it into the solution process" (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Algorithm of mental activity of students in solving creative problems

The ability to find the necessary information and apply it in creative activity is a mandatory requirement of the employer for a modern specialist, because the transition from knowledge to action happens much faster. Therefore, modern information communication technologies and computer-aided design systems are one of the necessary tools and pedagogical conditions that provide practical guidance using new information technologies and systems.

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and the educational and training process, expands communication opportunities, "fulfills the needs of functional interaction of educational subjects" [21].

We consider the ability and willingness to communicate online as a competence and a "multifunctional and flexible tool for professional reflection", which increases the scope for professional self-development and systematically organizes the future teacher, requires having intellectual, communicative, reflexive, moral qualities.

As a result, the subject-subject interaction changes, the role of the future teacher is not only as a carrier of social experience, but also as a person who studies the latest experience, conducts scientific research, interprets modern trends, also increases as an active person who tests achievements professionally.

Comparing the pedagogical activity of an expert primary school teacher and a future primary school teacher, it is necessary to emphasize the similarities and differences of the types of professional and creative activities determined by the content of educational programs (Table 1).

Table 1

Professional - creative activities

Pedagogical	Specialist teacher	Future teacher
education and methodology; management ; scientific research ; project	creativity and activity; organization and management; educational process; scientific research	formation of research and creativity; educational learning process and management learning process; experimental research

A graduate of higher education institution is known to be creative, it is required to be ready to solve tasks. Therefore, the modern requirements for professional and creative activity are the conceptual basis of creating creative competence.

The creative activity of pedagogical higher education institutions is related to the uniqueness of the state policy in the field of education, regional characteristics, fundamental and branch sciences. For example, employer of the graduates of higher educational institutions pay attention to the innovative way of creative and personal development of each future specialist, his ability to direct and organize his activities.

Table 2 shows the requirements of employers for graduates of higher educational institutions of pedagogy.

Table 2

The requirements of an employer for the level of creative knowledge of the future specialist of educational institutions

No	Content of requirements
1.	Knowledge of the theoretical foundations of special and specialized sciences.
2.	Ability to transform acquired knowledge into innovative technologies.
3.	Being able to independently find new information, perceive and analyze it, taking into account existing legislation and socio-legal norms.
4.	Ability to work with global information sources based on computer and information and communication technology tools.

5.	Ability to make decisions in ambiguous, standard and non-standard situations and complex professional conditions.
6.	Competence in computer-aided design systems.
7.	To have systematic analysis methods.
8.	To have the qualification to conduct scientific research.
9.	To have own software complexes for designing pedagogical solutions.
10.	To have adequate methods of professional communication and behavior, ability to cooperate and work in a group for a common result.
11.	Ability to be creative and innovative in solving professional tasks.
12.	Explain the directions and main directions of the development of primary education.
13.	Determining the need for information, correctly using the necessary information and solving specific tasks, giving them a professional assessment.

The creative competence of the students of pedagogical higher educational institution is the competent management of students' educational, research and professional activities.

The analysis of scientific works on the problem of formation of educational skills (O.A. Abdullina, N.V. Kuzmina, V.A. Slastenin, L.F. Spirin, etc.) showed that educational and research skills have a common important feature.

In traditional education, more attention is paid to the formation of study skills. In modern conditions, in the innovative training of future specialists, scientific research becomes an integral part of the educational process, and therefore the development of scientific skills of students is considered urgent.

V.A. Slastenin believed that the most important task of training future specialists is the formation of methodological culture, development of research skills. Some scientists (V.V. Uspensky, N.M. Yakovleva) consider research skills to be a set of skills to compare, analyze, identify, generalize, draw conclusions, etc. According to others (V.I. Andreev, Ye.I. Barchuk, L.V. Khivinseva), research skills are the ability to conduct scientific and empirical research in various subject areas, to use scientific methods to solve educational problems.

For our research, information on general theoretical and special subjects is updated in the process of studying special subjects in the formation of necessary skills of students. Students studying at a higher education institution are educated in an active attitude towards the teaching profession, practice is implemented, professional motives, methodical culture, research skills and qualities of the researcher are developed at high level.

Within the framework of the competency-based approach, we have identified the modern trends in the development of higher education: the transition from teaching to learning; changing the tasks of higher education related to the intensity of knowledge; increasing the role of information, the role of teamwork, subjective position and independence, and the powers of a specialist. The design and implementation of pedagogical conditions is considered by us as a method of educational effectiveness of the educational process, which makes it not only algorithmic, programmable, but also creative.

It was also considered that the most important principles of the formation of creative competence are the scientific validity of information, consistency, integrity, and the competent solution of pedagogical problems. The developing nature of education includes the improvement and dynamics of the educational process through the use of competency-based, creative, person-

oriented, system activity, pedagogical, task-based approaches and manifests itself in the formation of a person with creative competence.

The analysis of the conducted studies shows that the improvement of the system of defined pedagogical conditions helps in the purposeful, systematic formation of a competitive personality. The absence of any component relatively lowers the level of motivational readiness of students to solve the problem of forming creative competence. All this is the basis for the development of the concept and model of formation of creative competence of students of pedagogical higher education institution.

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